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Study on process and effective factors of high power disk laser welding for stainless steel with 10 mm thickness

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Abstract: To realize the single pass laser welding for 304 stainless steel with 10 mm thickness, full penetration welding process experiments had been carried out on the disk laser welding equipment with 10 kW laser power. The effects on the weld quality of welding speed, defocus length, laser power were studied. The appearance and dimension of the weld cross section were observed by optical microscope. The results showed that there was ablation on the top and bottom surface of welding bead when the welding speed was lower and there was root hump on the bottom surface of welding bead when the welding speed was higher. The defocusing length affected the focus position. When the defocus position under the top surface, it might decrease the energy efficiency using larger defocus length and it might lead to ablate using lower defocus length. For the workpiece with 10 mm thickness, it was better to have a defocus length of -3 mm. The laser power had great influence on weld penetration. It couldn't form a full penetration weld when the laser power was lower. Tensile strength results showed that the tensile strength average was 639.6 MPa, yield strength average was 297.6 MPa, and elongation average was 61.2%, which reached 95.5%, 99.2%, 95.5% of the base material respectively.

Key words: welding, high power, disk laser, stainless steel, tensile properties

Effect of pin shapes on temperature field in friction stir welding

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Abstract: A fully coupled thermo-mechanical model was adopted to study the effect of conical pin and cylindrical pin on weld temperature field in friction stir welding. The results showed that under the same conditions, the shoulder generated more heat than pin. When the thickness increased, the temperature curve gradually decreased. The temperature field curve was Ω shape. The advancing side temperature was higher than the retreating side. The top surface temperature curve was a platform shape in the shoulder, and the inside and the bottom surface curve was a mountain shape. Under the same conditions, the heat production of conical pin was higher than that of cylindrical pin. With the distance from the weld line increased, the difference of temperature was greater.

Key words: friction stir welding, stir pin, weld temperature field, aluminium alloy

Effects of ultrasonic impact treatment and post weld heat treatment on welding residual stresses in large-thickness nuclear power steel joints

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Abstract: Four Q390B and Q345D welded joints with large-thickness were manufactured and treated with ultrasonic impact treatment (UIT) and post weld heat treatment (PWHT). Hole-drilling method and X-ray diffraction method (XRD) were used to measure the as-welded surface stresses and the surface stresses after UIT and PWHT. The effects of UIT and PWHT on welding residual stresses were investigated. Research results showed that the transverse and longitudinal tensile stresses with a large magnitude ranging from 400~550 MPa decrease to compressive stresses of -200~-400 MPa. The stress reduction magnitude after UIT reached 700~800 MPa. In addition, the stresses in the region beyond the treated area were hardly affected by UIT. After PWHT, the residual stresses in the weld and base metal presented a almost uniform distribution with the peak tensile stress smaller than 100 MPa and the maximum reduction magnitude was about 400 MPa.

Key words: nuclear power structural steel, welding residual stress, post weld heat treatment, ultrasonic impact treatment

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厚 10 mm 不锈钢大功率碟片激光焊接及影响因素研究

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摘要: 为了实现 10 mm 厚 304 不锈钢的单道激光焊接, 在 10 kW 碟片激光焊接设备上进行了全熔透焊接工艺试验研究, 分析了不同焊接速度、离焦量、激光功率对焊接质量的影响。在显微镜下观察焊缝横截面形貌及测量几何尺寸。结果表明, 焊接速度较低时, 上下表面容易出现烧蚀, 焊接速度较高时, 会出现底部驼峰; 离焦量影响激光聚焦位置, 负离焦较大时会降低激光能量利用率, 负离焦较小时会导致表面烧蚀, 对于 10 mm 厚工件, 离焦量为 -3 mm 时较好。激光功率对焊缝熔深影响较大, 激光功率较小时不足以形成全熔透焊缝。拉伸试验结果表明, 焊缝抗拉强度平均为 639.6 MPa, 达到母材抗拉强度的 95.5%; 屈服强度平均为 297.6 MPa, 达到母材屈服强度的 99.2%; 伸长率平均为 61.2%, 达到母材伸长率的 95.5%。

关键词: 焊接; 大功率; 碟片激光; 不锈钢; 拉伸性能

中图分类号: TG456.7 文献标志码: B

0 前言

随着固体激光器的发展, 激光器输出功率及光束质量显著提高, 尤其是大功率碟片激光器、光纤激光器的出现, 极大地促进了大功率激光焊接技术的发展^[1-3], 使得厚板金属材料的单道激光焊接技术应用越来越广^[4-6]。

然而, 在厚板焊接过程中, 容易产生塌陷、气孔、底部驼峰等缺陷, 影响焊接接头质量^[7]。陈根余等人针对 10 kW 级光纤激光焊接的表面质量及底部驼峰形成进行了研究^[8], P Haug 等人采用 16 kW 的碟片激光设备研究了 12 mm 碳钢焊接过程的底部驼峰现象^[9], Y Kawahito 等人采用 10 kW 光纤激光设备研究了 8 mm 不锈钢的激光焊接特性^[10]。当前, 中厚板材料单道激光焊接还存在着较多问题, 有必要进一步深入研究分析。

本文采用 10 mm 厚 304 不锈钢为焊接材料, 在单道激光全熔透焊接的条件下, 研究了工艺参数对接头几何尺寸及缺陷形成的影响。

1 试验设备与材料

试验设备如图 1 所示, 采用 Trumpf Trudisk 10002 型碟片激光器, 最大输出功率 10 kW, 波长 1 030 nm, 光束质量为 8 mm·mrad, 功率稳定性±1%。在试验过程中, 传输光纤芯径为 200 μm, 准直镜焦距为 200 mm, 聚焦镜焦距为 200 mm。机械手采用德国 KUKA KR60 六轴机器人, 带动焊接头移动进行激光焊接试验, 如图 2 所示。

图 1 碟片激光器

图 2 焊接装置

焊接试验材料采用 10 mm 厚 304 不锈钢, 规格为 200 mm×120 mm×10 mm, 其化学成分见表 1。

表 1 试验材料化学成分(质量分数)(%)

C	Mn	P	S	Si	Cr	Ni	Fe
0.07	2.0	0.035	0.03	0.075	18	9	余量

试验前将焊接端面车铣平整, 用无水乙醇清洗表面。焊接过程中, 正面和背面均采用 Ar 气进行保护, 流量分别为 15 L/min 和 20 L/min。试验工艺参

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数见表2。在焊后的试件上取样做成金相试样，采用FeCl₃+HCl溶液进行腐蚀，并在金相显微镜下观察焊缝截面形貌，并在金相显微镜下测量尺寸参数。按照GB/T 2651—2008标准设计力学性能测试件，采用GP-TS2000M型拉伸机进行接头拉伸测试，拉伸试样尺寸如图3所示。

表2 试验工艺参数

试验号	激光功率/kW	焊接速度/(m·min ⁻¹)	离焦量/mm
1	10.0	0.040	-5
2	10.0	0.050	-5
3	10.0	0.040	-3
4	10.0	0.050	-3
5	10.0	0.055	-3
6	10.0	0.060	-3
7	10.0	0.065	-3
8	10.0	0.050	-1
9	9.0	0.050	-3
10	8.0	0.050	-3

图3 拉伸试样尺寸

2 试验结果

用表2中的工艺参数进行试验。通过改变焊接速度、离焦量、激光功率等参数，获得不同的焊缝，试验完成后拍摄焊缝表面、背面、横截面。

为了研究焊接速度对焊缝形貌的影响，采用表2中的工艺参数进行了不同离焦量下改变焊接速度的试验。图4为采用1, 2组试验参数获得的焊缝形貌，离焦量为-5 mm，激光功率10 kW；图5为采用3, 4, 5, 6, 7组试验参数获得的焊缝形貌，离焦量为-3 mm，激光功率10 kW。

图4 离焦量-5 mm时不同焊接速度的试验结果

图5 离焦量-3 mm时不同焊接速度下获得的试验结果

为进一步对比不同离焦量下获得的焊缝形貌，采用表2中第8组参数进行了焊接试验，在离焦量-1 mm，激光功率10 kW，焊接速度0.050 m/min时获得的焊缝形貌如图6所示。

图6 离焦量-1 mm时获得的试验结果

为了研究不同激光功率对焊缝形貌的影响，在第4组试验结果的基础上，改变激光功率进行试验，即在离焦量为-3 mm，焊接速度为0.050 m/min时，采用8, 9 kW的激光功率进行焊接试验，焊接工艺参数采用表2中第9, 10组数据，获得的焊缝形貌如图7所示。

(a) 激光功率9 kW

图7 不同激光功率的试验结果

3 分析与讨论

3.1 焊接速度的影响

采用表2中的3, 4, 5, 6, 7组参数进行试验, 得到的焊缝形貌如图8所示。对比3, 4, 5, 6, 7组试验结果, 随着焊接速度的提高, 焊缝上表面、下表面、内部宽度均呈减小的趋势。分析认为, 焊接速度提高, 线能量减小, 金属熔化量减少, 熔池变小, 减小了焊缝的宽度。

图8 焊接速度对焊缝形貌的影响

在焊接速度为0.04 m/min时, 表面及底部出现了严重的烧蚀现象。此时线能量过大, 在工件表面导致金属大量蒸发, 并导致深熔小孔内部液态金属温度过高, 蒸汽压力过大, 使得熔池内熔融金属受到向下的压力急剧增大, 液态金属从焊缝底部喷射出来, 导致焊缝底部出现烧蚀, 形成内凹。在焊接速度为0.05 m/min时, 焊缝表面及底部平整, 但焊缝底部未形成凸出部分, 在此焊接速度下, 在熔池内部蒸汽压力作用下, 依然有部分金属从底部喷射, 没有在焊缝底部形成余高。在焊接速度为0.055 m/min及0.06 m/min时, 焊缝表面及底部均匀, 没有出现凹坑及驼峰, 此时, 深熔小孔内压力处于平衡状态, 熔池内的液态金属在小孔内循环流动, 处于稳定状态。在焊接速度为0.065 m/min时, 焊缝底部出现了连续性的驼峰。

分析认为, 在焊接速度0.04~0.060 m/min时, 当焊接速度提高, 线能量减小, 能够有效改善焊缝表面及底部的烧蚀情况。当焊接速度提高至0.065 m/min时, 线能量过小, 导致焊缝熔池内部熔融金属的温度较低, 表面张力不足以克服熔池液态金属的重力, 因此液态金属无法回到熔池, 在底部聚集而形成驼峰。

3.2 离焦量对焊缝成形的影响

离焦量是指激光聚焦点与工件上表面的距离, 图9所示为离焦量-1, -3, -5 mm时激光束在焊接过程中的聚焦位置。当离焦量为负时, 激光束聚焦位置在熔池内部, 聚焦点的能量密度最大。对比2, 4, 8组试验, 可以发现, 在相同激光功率、焊接速度的情况下, 形成的焊缝有着较大的区别。在离焦量为-1 mm时, 焊缝表面出现了严重的烧蚀现象, 焊缝底部出现了驼峰。离焦量为-3 mm时, 焊缝上下表面平整, 底部余高很小; 离焦量为-5 mm时, 焊缝底部出现了轻微的驼峰现象。

图9 不同离焦量下的聚焦位置

分析认为, 离焦量为-1 mm时, 激光聚焦点离工件表面很近, 聚焦点的能量密度很大, 容易将表面金属材料瞬间汽化蒸发, 在表面形成凹陷, 同时, 小孔内形成的金属蒸汽容易在表面材料汽化时以飞溅的形式喷射出来, 减小了内部气体压力, 使得熔池内部的熔融金属往熔池底部流动的速度降低, 造成底部液态金属减少和温度较低, 形成底部驼峰。当离焦量为-3 mm时, 聚焦点位置下移, 聚焦点产生的蒸汽被小孔包裹着, 在小孔内形成较大的蒸汽压力, 以此促进液态金属在熔池内的流动。当离焦量为-5 mm时, 焦平面在工件中心位置, 在工件表面的激光功率密度较低, 为形成深熔小孔, 需要消

耗较多的激光能量,因此,到达聚焦点位置的激光能量相对减少。

对比离焦量-5, -3 mm的情况,2种条件下,焊缝表面没有出现烧蚀的情况,但在离焦量为-5 mm时,焊缝底部出现了驼峰现象,此时激光能量利用率不如离焦量-3 mm时的。对比1, 3组试验,也可以发现,相同激光功率及焊接速度的情况下,在离焦量-3 mm时到达底部的能量较多,容易造成底部喷射,形成底部咬边。当增大速度后,能够改善这种情况,因此,离焦量-3 mm时,在获得相同熔深的情况下,焊接效率更高。对比3种离焦量下的焊缝形貌,认为离焦量-3 mm较为合适。

3.3 激光功率对焊缝成形的影响

对比4, 9, 10组试验,可以发现,激光功率降低,焊缝成形变化较大,当激光功率为9 kW时,焊缝底部出现了余高,与4组试验结果相比,到达深熔小孔内部的激光功率降低,内部蒸汽压力减小,熔融金属不会从底部喷射出去。当激光功率8 kW时,焊缝没有熔透,此时,激光功率较低,没有足够的能量来熔化10 mm厚的金属。因此,在一定的焊接速度下,激光功率必须选择合适的值,否则,容易出现底部喷射或未熔透。

3.4 拉伸性能测试

选择焊缝成形较好的4, 5, 6组试件进行拉伸性能测试。按图加工拉伸试件,将试件上下表面打磨平整。拉伸测试结果见表3,焊缝抗拉强度平均639.6 MPa,达到母材抗拉强度的95.5%;屈服强度平均为297.6 MPa,达到母材屈服强度的99.2%;伸长率平均为61.2%,达到母材伸长率的95.5% (62%)。

表3 拉伸测试结果

序号	抗拉强度/MPa	屈服强度/MPa	伸长率/%
4	639	296	60.3
5	639	297	62.0
6	641	300	61.3
平均值	639.6	297.6	61.2
母材	670	300	62.0

4 结论

(1) 焊接速度较慢时,上下表面容易出现烧蚀,

焊接速度较快时,会出现底部驼峰。

(2) 离焦量影响激光聚焦位置,较大的负离焦量会降低激光能量利用率,较小的负离焦量容易导致表面烧蚀,对于10 mm厚工件,离焦量为-3 mm时较好。

(3) 激光功率对焊缝熔深影响较大,激光功率较小时不足以形成全熔透焊缝。

(4) 拉伸测试结果表明,焊缝抗拉强度平均639.6 MPa,达到母材抗拉强度的95.5%;屈服强度平均为297.6 MPa,达到母材屈服强度的99.2%;伸长率平均为61.2%,达到母材伸长率的95.5%。

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